

Merocyanines Derived from Oxazolone

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Merocyanines, derived from different 2-aryl oxazolone as the acidic nuclei and various basic nuclei like 2-methyl 4-phenyl thiazole, 2-methyl benzothiazole, quinoline-2, quinoline-4 and alpha-picoline have been studied with a view to examining the effect of different substituents present at the position-2 of the oxazolone nucleus on the absorption and sensitisation spectra.

In the previous paper¹ it was seen that when a *p*-nitro phenyl group is present in the position-2 of the oxazolone, the merocyanine derived from it absorbs at a longer wavelength than the one which is derived from 2-phenyl oxazolone. In the present investigation we have examined the effect of three electronegative groups on absorption maxima, namely 2-*p*-methoxy phenyl, 2-*p*-chlorophenyl and 2-*p*-tolyl oxazolones which were used as acidic nuclei. An examination of Table I reveals that when a *p*-tolyl or *p*-methoxy phenyl group is present the dye absorbs at a lower wavelength compared to corresponding dye containing a phenyl nucleus only. Further, when a chlorophenyl group is present in the 2-position of the oxazolone nucleus the dye absorbs at a slightly higher wavelength than the corresponding dyes derived from 2-phenyl oxazolone.

The sensitisation spectra of these dyes were determined by standard procedure using a constant deviation spectrograph using a density wedge. In the Table I are given the result of such study. An examination of the Table I indicates that these dyes were good photographic sensitisers in the region where they show maximum absorption. From the data of sensitisation spectra it can be seen that when an anisoyl group is present in the oxazolone nucleus it renders the plate more sensitive than the corresponding tolyl analogue. Further, it is seen that the presence of a halogen atom in the oxazolone nucleus makes the dyes less suitable for use as photographic sensitisers.

In order to prepare these dyes, first the substituted benzoyl glycine was prepared by benzoylating glycine. The resultant substituted benzoyl glycines were condensed with either ethyl orthoformate or trimethoxy propene in acetic anhydride medium to give 4-ethoxy methylene or 4-(3'-methoxy allylidene) oxazolones respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Ethoxy methylene oxazolone : The intermediates of the type 2-*p*-substituted phenyl-4-ethoxymethylene oxazolones and 2-*p*-substituted phenyl-4-(3'-methoxy allylidene) oxazolones were prepared by the method given by Rout *et al.*².

1. This *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 625.
2. M. K. Rout, *et al.*, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 9.

TABLE I

B—Basic nucleus.

Compound No.	Nature of R	Nature of Basic nucleus	Value of 'n'	λ_{\max}	Sens. Range	Sens. max.	Quality of sensn.
1.	<i>p</i> -Anisoyl	Benzothiazole	1	515	500—640	560	Good
2.		Quinoline-2	1	530	550—630	610	Fair
3.		Quinoline-4	1	615	580—640	630	Fair
4.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	1	525	500—660	550	Good
5.		α -Picoline	1	510	—	—	—
6.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Benzothiazole	1	520	500—610	580	Good
7.		Quinoline-2	1	535	550—630	580	Poor
8.		Quinoline-4	1	618	550—650	630	Good
9.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	1	528	500—630	550	Good
10.		α -Picoline	1	512	500—620	550	Fair
11.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	Benzothiazole	1	525	500—610	580	Good
12.		Quinoline-2	1	550	550—650	610	Good
13.		Quinoline-4	1	525	580—640	620	Poor
14.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	1	535	550—630	580	Poor
15.		α -Picoline	1	520	—	—	—
16.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Benzothiazole	2	612	610—700	660	Good
17.		Quinoline-2	2	635	610—690	680	Poor
18.		Quinoline-4	2	705	630—700	690	Poor
19.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	2	620	580—690	660	Good
20.		α -Picoline	2	612	580—690	630	Poor
21.	<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	Benzothiazole	2	620	610—700	660	Good
22.		Quinoline-2	2	655	610—700	690	Poor
23.		Quinoline-4	2	710	630—700	680	Good
24.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	2	625	580—700	660	Good
25.		α -Picoline	2	620	—	—	—
26.	<i>p</i> -Anisoyl	Benzothiazole	2	608	—	—	—
27.		Quinoline-2	2	630	—	—	—
28.		Quinoline-4	2	700	—	—	—
29.		4-Ph-2-Methiazole	2	615	—	—	—
30.		α -Picoline	2	600	—	—	—

TABLE II

Name of the glycine	Ethoxy methylene compound		3'-methoxy allylidene compound	
	M.P. (°C)	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C.)	Yield (%)
<i>p</i> -Anisoyl	272	75	210(d)*	50
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	186	60	163	62
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	195	78	188	55

*(d) denotes decomposition.

The merocyanines were prepared as follows : Equimolecular quantities of the appropriate ethoxy methylene or 3'-methoxy allylidene derivatives of the oxazolone and the quaternary salts of 2-methyl heterocyclic compounds were dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and triethylamine (1 mole) was added. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for five to ten minutes with reflux. On cooling solids, which separated out, were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

TABLE III

No. of compound	Nature of ring 'B'	Nature of 'n'	R = <i>p</i> -Anisoyl λ_{max}	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
						Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1.	Benzothiazole	1	515	50	188 (d)*	65.8	65.6	4.37	4.60
2.	Quinoline-2	1	530	54	198	73.7	73.86	5.02	5.20
3.	Quinoline-4	1	615	55	202	73.7	73.95	5.02	5.35
4.	4-Ph-thiazole	1	525	45	200 (d)	67.6	67.48	4.61	4.75
5.	α -Picoline	1	510	40	218 (d)	71.1	70.3	5.51	5.70
26.	Benzothiazole	2	608	50	198 (d)	67.3	67.7	4.59	4.61
27.	Quinoline-2	2	630	50	210 (d)	75.0	74.56	5.20	5.45
28.	Quinoline-4	2	700	48	196 (d)	75.0	74.8	5.20	5.50
29.	4-Ph-thiazole	2	615	42	206 (d)	69.2	69.5	6.70	6.60
30.	α -Picoline	2	600	40	228 (d)	71.8	71.6	5.67	5.75

*(d) denotes decomposition.

TABLE IV

No. of compound	Nature of ring 'B'	Nature of 'n'	R = <i>p</i> -Toluyλ _{max}	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
						Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
6.	Benzothiazole	1	520	65	215	68.5	68.6	4.57	4.42
7.	Quinoline-2	1	535	68	238	77.1	77.3	5.20	5.10
8.	Quinoline-4	1	618	70	242	77.1	77.25	5.20	5.26
9.	4-Ph-thiazole	1	528	62	180	70.5	70.35	4.84	4.97
10.	α-Picoline	1	512	50	207	73.9	73.78	5.82	5.92
16.	Benzothiazole	2	612	55	212(d)*	70.2	70.15	4.84	4.86
17.	Quinoline-2	2	635	52	202	78.2	78.1	5.43	5.50
18.	Quinoline-4	2	705	55	232(d)*	78.2	78.04	5.43	5.65
19.	4-Ph. Thiazole	2	620	45	185	72.0	72.2	5.00	5.00
20.	α-Picoline	2	612	40	218(d)*	75.4	75.35	5.97	5.85

*(d)—denotes decomposition.

TABLE V

No. of compound	Nature of ring 'B'	Nature of 'n'	R = <i>p</i> -chloro phenyl λ _{max}	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
						Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
11.	Benzothiazole	1	525	65	198	61.6	61.85	3.51	3.64
12.	Quinoline-2	1	550	60	224	69.9	69.71	4.14	4.22
13.	Quinoline-4	1	625	65	262	69.9	69.56	4.14	4.28
14.	4-Ph. thiazole	1	535	52	210	63.9	63.81	3.80	3.95
15.	α-Picoline	1	520	50	215	65.3	65.52	4.48	4.92
21.	Benzothiazole	2	620	55	186	63.6	63.56	3.56	3.70
22.	Quinoline-2	2	655	50	204	71.1	71.2	4.38	4.39
23.	Quinoline-4	2	710	50	236	71.1	71.25	4.38	4.39
24.	4-Ph-thiazole	2	625	48	208	65.7	65.9	4.28	4.35
35.	α-Picoline	2	620	40	242	67.4	67.56	4.73	4.85

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